

SPEcification, Analysis & Re-calibration of High Energy pARticle Data (SPEARHEAD)

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List of Acronyms

ACE	Advanced Composition Explorer
AMS	Alpha Magnet Spectrometer
CME	Coronal Mass Ejection
CR	Cosmic Rays
EPEAD	Energetic Proton, Electron and Alpha Detector
EPHIN	Electron, Proton and Helium Instrument
ERNE	Energetic and Relativistic Nuclei and Electron experiment
GCR	Galactic Cosmic Ray
GLE	Ground Level Enhancement
GOES	Geostationary Operational Environmental Satellites
HEPAD	High Energy Proton and Alpha Detector
HET	High Energy Telescope
IGRF	International Geomagnetic Reference Field
IMF	Interplanetary Magnetic Field
ISS	International Space Station
NM	Neutron Monitor
OTSO	Open-source geomagneToSphere prOpagation
PAD	Pitch-Angle Distribution
PAMELA	Payload for Antimatter Matter Exploration and Light-nuclei Astrophysics
pfu	particle flux unit
SEISS	Space Environment In-Situ Suite
SEP	Solar Energetic Particle
SGPS	Solar and Galactic Proton Sensor
SOHO	Solar and Heliospheric Observatory
SoIO	Solar Orbiter
SPEARHEAD	SPeCification, Analysis & Re-calibration of High Energy pArticle Data
SQ	Science Question
STEREO	Solar Terrestrial Relations Observatory
TSY	Tsyganenko storm-time model
WP	Work Package
YF	Yield Function

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This Deliverable presents a consolidated methodology for comparing ground-based and space-borne observations of high-energy Solar Energetic Particle (SEP) events. The approach is first illustrated using the well-studied case of GLE71 on 17 May 2012, for which the comparison between NM measurements and Payload for Antimatter Matter Exploration and Light-nuclei Astrophysics (PAMELA) observations was previously demonstrated in detail. Building on this foundation, we extend the analysis to two new events investigated within the SPEcification, Analysis & Re-calibration of High Energy pArticle Data (SPEARHEAD) project: the sub-GLE on 7 March 2012 and the significant GLE74 on 11 May 2024. The latter occurred during the deep phase of a pronounced Forbush decrease and one of the strongest geomagnetic storms on record, rendering its analysis particularly challenging. For these new events, we compare NM observations with measurements from GOES and SOHO/EPHIN, thereby broadening the framework established with GLE71. In addition to validating the NM reconstructions, the inter-comparison between GOES and EPHIN in overlapping energy ranges provides an independent cross-check of spectral slopes, intensity levels, and high-energy rollover behavior, strengthening confidence in the derived broadband proton spectra. Both GLE71 and GLE74 exhibited complex and highly anisotropic particle fluxes, while the sub-GLE event produced a low-intensity, short-duration signal that pushed the limits of standard analysis techniques. In this work, we apply the full-spectrum method to NM data and validate the results against satellite measurements from GOES for GLE74 and the sub-GLE. These new analyses build upon earlier NM–PAMELA comparisons performed for GLE71, demonstrating the robustness and transferability of the methodology across different spacecraft datasets and event intensities. The results underscore the value of cross-calibration between ground-based and space-borne instruments and highlight the capabilities of the global NM network in detecting and characterizing both strong and weak SEP events. Overall, the findings emphasize the necessity of accounting for particle anisotropy in event reconstruction, demonstrate the importance of multi-instrument spectral validation, and reaffirm the critical role of the NM network in advancing high-energy SEP diagnostics. This work constitutes **Deliverable 3.4 (D3.4)** of the SPEARHEAD project.

1 Introduction

Ground Level Enhancements (GLEs), as observed by neutron monitors (NMs), constitute a fundamental component in the study of the acceleration and propagation of high-energy solar energetic particles (SEPs) associated with solar eruptive events. GLEs are characterized as rare but significant phenomena during which SEPs — predominantly protons — are accelerated to relativistic energies, often exceeding 500 MeV. At such energies, these particles possess sufficient rigidity (energy) to traverse Earth's magnetosphere and penetrate the atmosphere, where their interactions generate secondary particles detectable by ground-based NMs (e.g. [Shea & Smart 2012](#); [Papaioannou 2023](#)).

These events serve as unequivocal evidence that solar eruptive processes are capable of accelerating protons to energies far surpassing 100 MeV. Detailed analyses of the temporal evolution, spatial distribution, and intensity profiles of GLEs enable researchers to disentangle the complex mechanisms underlying particle acceleration. Such analyses are fundamental in differentiating between impulsive, flare-associated acceleration and prolonged, shock-mediated acceleration driven by coronal mass ejections (CMEs), as outlined in recent work ([Kouloumvakos et al. 2024](#)).

To obtain a comprehensive understanding of SEP acceleration and transport, it is essential to characterize the full energy spectrum of these particles, from the low-energy range measured by space-based instruments to the high-energy regime accessible only through the neutron monitor network (NMDB; www.nmdb.eu) ([Kocharov et al. 2023](#)). While spacecrafts/instruments such as the SOHO/Energetic and Relativistic Nuclei and Electron experiment (ERNE), GOES/SGPS, Solar Terrestrial Relations Observatory (STEREO)/High Energy Telescope (HET) and recently Solar Orbiter (SolO)/HET provide in situ measurements of SEP fluxes up to \sim hundred MeV ([Desai & Giacalone 2016](#); [Papaioannou et al. 2022](#); [Kouloumvakos et al. 2024](#)), they generally lack sensitivity to the highest-energy SEPs observed during GLEs. NMs, on the other hand, are uniquely sensitive to SEPs in the \sim 500 MeV to multi-GeV range, filling the critical observational gap in the energy spectrum. Therefore, the synergistic use of both space- and ground-based observations is indispensable for accurately reconstructing SEP energy spectra and determining spectral breaks, rollovers, or multiple acceleration components ([Tylka & Dietrich 2009](#); [Mishev et al. 2018](#)).

By leveraging the multi-station NM network, researchers can reconstruct spectral and angular characteristics of incoming SEPs. These reconstructions yield critical constraints on the location and efficiency of the acceleration region. Specifically, the energy spectra and anisotropy patterns inferred from NM data provide insights into both the initial acceleration conditions near the Sun and the subsequent interplanetary transport processes ([Mishev et al. 2014](#); [Papaioannou et al. 2025](#)). GLE observations are further employed to infer solar particle release times and delineate transport dynamics through the heliosphere, informed by detailed timing studies of particle arrival at globally distributed monitoring sites ([Masson et al. 2009](#); [Musset et al. 2023](#)). These timing relationships facilitate estimations of the SEP injection profile at the Sun and allow for the assessment of the modulating influence of heliospheric structures ([Masson et al. 2012](#); [Moraal & McCracken 2012](#)).

Within this framework, GLEs provide a uniquely valuable observational window into all three core Science Questions (SQs) posed by the SPEARHEAD project:

1. How are protons accelerated beyond 100 MeV and electrons beyond 1 MeV in solar eruptions?
2. What are the release times and spectral characteristics of near-relativistic particles from solar eruptions?
3. How do coronal and interplanetary structures affect the transport processes of very high energetic particles?

Nonetheless, the study of primary Cosmic Rays (CR) particle characteristics, specifically SEPs, from ground-based data records is a major challenge. As noted, a convenient instrument for such a purpose

is a **NM**. In general, the **NM** is an instrument that measures the intensity of high-energy **CR** particles. It allows continuous accumulation of recordings of the secondary **CR** hadron component. As a result, **NM** measurements provide a basis for studying variations in the intensity of the interplanetary **CR** spectrum. Due to the decreasing energy spectrum of the primary **CRs**, **NMs** are particularly sensitive to the lower-energy part of the **CR** spectrum, typically between 1 and 20 GeV.

The introduction of the **NM** as a continuous recorder of the primary **CR** intensity was enabled by the pioneering design of Simpson (Simpson et al. 1953). Based on that design, a 12-tube **NM** was constructed during the International Geophysical Year (IGY) 1957–1958 (Simpson 1957). The IGY **NM** was deployed worldwide as a cosmic ray detector. Over time, its design was optimized through a significant increase in the amount of lead per unit area, leading to higher counting rates and ultimately the development of the NM64 design (Hatton & Carmichael 1964). An illustration of its main components is provided in Fig. 1. The measurements performed by the worldwide network of **NMs** are critical for estimating the spectral and angular characteristics of **SEPs** near Earth. To relate **NM** count rates to the incident particle flux, it is necessary to apply a well-defined **NM** Yield Function (**YF**). This function accounts for the full complexity of atmospheric cascade development, the propagation of secondary particles through the atmosphere, and the detection efficiency of the **NM** for different particle species and energies (Bütikofer 2018).

Figure 1: Sketch of a standard 6NM64 **NM**. The **NM** consists of a moderator, which reduces the energy of neutrons i.e. increasing the probability of an absorption inside the counter while also providing a reflecting medium for low energy neutrons. The moderator material is usually low density polyethelene. The Lead Producer surrounds the moderator, providing a thick large-nucleus target for incident particles. A large nucleus such as lead is preferred as the neutron production rate per unit mass of a material is roughly proportional to the mass. Surrounding the lead is an outer moderator, usually referred to as to the Reflector, which serves to contain low energy neutrons produced in interactions within the lead as well as to reject unwanted low energy neutrons (external evaporation neutrons) produced in the local surroundings from entering into the detector. Adapted from (Bütikofer 2018) under CC BY 4.0.

Direct **SEP** measurements in space are carried out by high-precision instruments such as the Alpha Magnet Spectrometer (**AMS**)-02 on board the International Space Station (**ISS**) (Bindi 2015) and the **PAMELA** experiment (Bruno et al. 2018). However, a significant discrepancy has persisted between the spectral shapes derived from near-Earth space-based observations and those reconstructed using ground-based data (Klein & Dalla 2017). This mismatch arises from the complexity of cross-calibrating

different instruments and a notable gap in the overlapping energy coverage between spaceborne and ground-based detectors. Encouragingly, recent advances have expanded the energy range and sensitivity of several space-borne detectors. For example, [GOES](#) now measures protons up to 700 MeV ([Papaioannou et al. 2022, 2025](#)), specifically [GOES/SGPS](#) ([Kress et al. 2021](#)), and instruments like [SOHO/EPHIN](#) or [SoLO/HET](#) have shown possibilities to extend their capabilities to cover 1–900 MeV ([Kühl et al. 2017](#); [Kouloumvakos et al. 2024](#)). These improvements have enabled progress in bridging the observational gap and facilitating more reliable cross-calibration between space- and ground-based datasets. Herein, we report on the latest developments in such cross-calibration efforts, within the [SPEARHEAD](#) project, which are essential for the unified reconstruction of SEP spectra and the advancement of heliophysics modeling.

Consequently, [NM](#)-based measurements, while indirect, are indispensable for quantifying temporal and spectral variations in the interplanetary [CR](#) flux, especially in the higher-energy domain. When combined with direct space-based [SEP](#) observations, they enable a full-spectrum view of particle acceleration and propagation. This integrated approach is critical for addressing the core [SQs](#) of [SPEARHEAD](#), as it enhances our understanding of solar particle release processes, acceleration mechanisms, and interplanetary transport dynamics.

2 Modeling Ground-Level Enhancements Using the Global Neutron Monitor Network

To utilize a ground-based detector such as a [NM](#) as a primary tool for observing incoming [CR](#) particles of galactic and/or solar origin, a precise relationship must be established between the [NM](#) count rate and the primary [CR](#) flux ([Clem & Dorman 2000](#)). This relationship is governed by the [NM](#) response function and the spectral and angular properties of the incoming particles. The counting rate of a [NM](#) station is expressed as:

$$N(P_c, h, t) = \int_{P_c}^{\infty} \sum_i Y_i(P, h) J_i(P, t) dP = \int_{P_c}^{\infty} W_T(P, h, t) dP \quad (1)$$

where $N(P_c, h, t)$ represents the counting rate of the [NM](#), P_c is the local geomagnetic cutoff, h is the atmospheric depth and t represents time. The term $Y_i(P, h)$ represents the [NM](#) yield function ([YF](#)) for primaries of particle type i , $J_i(P, t)$ represents the rigidity spectrum of primary particle of type i at time t and W_T is the total differential response function.

The [NM](#) yield function ([YF](#)) is defined as:

$$Y_i(P, h) = \sum_i \int \int A_i(E, \theta) F_{i,j}(P, h, E, \theta) dE d\Omega \quad (2)$$

where $A_i(E, \theta)$ denotes the product of effective detector area and efficiency for secondary particles of energy E and angle θ , while $F_{i,j}$ is the differential flux of secondary particles (neutrons, protons, muons, pions) per primary i , E is respectively the secondary particle's energy, θ is the angle of incidence of secondaries and Ω is the solid angle. The [YF](#) incorporates both the propagation of particles through the Earth's atmosphere and the detection response of an [NM](#) against secondary particles such as neutrons, protons, muons, and pions.

In order to reveal the characteristics of [SEPs](#) leading to a [GLE](#) it is necessary to collect the available records from the global [NM](#) network and several space probes. The unfolding of the [SEP](#) spectra and angular distribution using ground-based records involves realistic modelling of the magnetospheric conditions and solar protons propagation, as well as the response of the [NM](#) network (see details in [Bütikofer 2018](#)). This is because the Earth's magnetosphere acts as a complex and dynamic filter, allowing or forbidding the entry of charged particles based on their rigidity and incident direction. To model

these effects, we employed the Open-source geomagneToSphere propagation (OTSO) tool (Larsen et al. 2023), a modern framework for tracing CR trajectories through the Earth's magnetosphere. OTSO builds upon decades of previous research and integrates both the internal and external geomagnetic field components. For the internal field, we adopt the International Geomagnetic Reference Field (IGRF) model (Alken et al. 2021), which captures the Earth's main field as generated by the geodynamo. For the external component—reflecting the influence of magnetospheric currents—we utilize the Tsyganenko storm-time model (TSY)01S (Tsyganenko et al. 2003), a variant of the original TSY01 (Tsyganenko 2002a,b), but specifically parameterized to better describe magnetic configurations during geomagnetic storms, while for quiet geomagnetospheric conditions we can employ as external magnetic field the Tsyganenko 89 model (TSY89) Tsyganenko (1989), which is a fairly simple semi-empirical model parameterised by the Kp index.

The most reliable model during strong geomagnetic storms is the TSY01S model, which accounts for transient current systems such as ring currents, magnetopause currents, and tail currents, which dominate the field structure during disturbed space weather conditions. This is particularly relevant for events like GLE74 which occurred under pronounced geomagnetic activity (Papaioannou et al. 2025). In such cases, the standard field models can significantly misrepresent the particle cutoff rigidity and asymptotic directions, leading to erroneous interpretation of the NM responses. TSY01S, however, provides a more reliable representation by incorporating real-time solar wind and geomagnetic input parameters.

The computation of asymptotic directions — the set of interplanetary directions from which primary particles can reach a given NM station — is vital. These directions, derived using OTSO and the magnetospheric field models, form the basis for mapping the observed NM signals to the actual solar particle distribution in space. Effectively, the geomagnetosphere serves as a natural directional and energy spectrometer, transforming isotropic or anisotropic SEP fluxes into NM count rate patterns across the global network (Bieber & Evenson 1995).

The global NM network's heterogeneous sensitivity to various energies and directional components of SEPs makes it a powerful tool for reconstructing SEP characteristics. Using a forward-modeling approach, we simulate NM responses by convolving an assumed primary CR spectrum $J(P, t)$ with the NM YF $Y(P, h)$ (for details see Clem & Dorman 2000). This synthetic response is then optimized against the actual NM measurements across m stations, varying n model parameters to minimize the discrepancy. As a result, following this procedure, it is possible to unfold the spectra, Pitch-Angle Distribution (PAD) and apparent source position of GLEs (Cramp et al. 1997; Bombardieri et al. 2006; Vashenyuk et al. 2006; Mishev et al. 2014)

In the general case, to accurately capture anisotropic SEP events, such as those with beam-like or bi-directional flux, the modelling includes oblique incidence of SEPs to the NM response (Clem 1997). The sky above each NM station is divided into angular sectors (see Fig. 2) and the contribution from each segment is computed individually, taking into account the detector's angular sensitivity. The relative count rate increase of a given NM during GLEs is modeled by:

$$\frac{\Delta N(P_{\text{cut}})}{N(t)} = \frac{\sum_k \int_{P_{\text{cut}}}^{P_{\text{max}}} J_{\text{sep}}(P, t) S_k(P) G_k(\alpha(P, t)) A_k(P) dP}{\sum_i \int_{P_{\text{cut}}}^{\infty} J_{\text{GCR}_i}(P, t) S_i(P) dP} \quad (3)$$

where $\Delta N(P_{\text{cut}})$ is the count rate increase due to solar particles, $N(t)$ is the count rate due to Galactic Cosmic Rays (GCRs), J_{sep} is the rigidity spectrum of SEPs, $J_{\text{GCR}_i}(P, t)$ is the rigidity spectrum of the i component (proton or α -particle, etc...) of GCRs at given time t , i.e. effectively accounting for the modulation, $G(\alpha(P, t))$ is the pitch angle distribution (PAD). Note that for GCRs the angular distribution is assumed to be isotropic thus $A(P)$ is a discrete function with $A(P)=1$ for allowed trajectories and $A(P)=0$ for forbidden trajectories (Cooke et al. 1991). Function $A(P)$ is derived during the asymptotic direction computations. P_{cut} is the minimum rigidity cut-off of the station, accordingly, P_{max} is the maximum rigidity of SEPs considered in the model, while for GCR $P_{\text{max}} = \infty$. S_k is the NM YF for vertical and for oblique incidence SEPs from various segments (see e.g. Fig. 2). The central segment corresponds to

Figure 2: Segments (from the center) of the sky over which the **NM** response was integrated during the modelling. Segment 1 (center) corresponds to vertical incidence, segments 2 (first from the central ring, North)–5 (first ring West), to 0–90–180–270 degrees inclination. Segments 6–9 and 10–13 correspond to an inclination of 30 and 45 degrees, respectively. Adapted from (Mishev 2023) under CC BY 4.0.

vertical incidence. Segments 2–5 represent SEPs with an inclination of 15 degrees and azimuth angles 0–90–180–270 degrees. Segments 6–9 and 10–13 correspond to an inclination of 30 and 45 degrees, respectively each with the same azimuth angles as in the 15 degrees inclination case. The asymptotic directions of the incoming SEPs for the different angles of incidence are computed for each segment separately, that is, we have in total 13 sets of asymptotic directions.

We note that a natural initial guess for the optimisation follows a plausible set of SEP spectra and angular distribution based on statistical analysis of a plethora of GLEs (Kocharov et al. 2023; Larsen & Mishev 2024), assuming the apparent source position along the IMF (Mishev & Usoskin 2016b; Kocharov et al. 2017), which is retrieved from space-borne measurements by Advanced Composition Explorer (ACE) (Smith et al. 1998).

The **NM** modelling, in the frame of this **deliverable (D3.4)**, is based on a new-generation of **NM YF** (Mishev et al. 2020) calibrated on direct particle measurements with **PAMELA** (Adriani et al. 2017) and **AMS-02** (Aguilar et al. 2021) space-borne experiments (for details see Koldobskiy & Mishev 2022, and the discussion therein). The new **NM YF** is also in very good agreement with latitude surveys and was recommended for **GLE** analysis (e.g. Nuntiyakul et al. 2018; Xaplanteris et al. 2021; Caballero-Lopez & Manzano 2022).

There are several criteria that determine the quality of the fit. One is the normalized residual (e.g. Himmelblau 1972; Dennis & Schnabel 1996) (see Equation 4), which is recommended to be employed for non-linear optimisations (e.g. Leonov & Yagola 1998; Golub et al. 1999; Yagola et al. 2002). Another

is the requirement that the normalized residual is uniformly distributed. Additionally, the fitting should aim for a relative difference of about 10–15% between the observed and calculated NM increases for each NM with a statistically significant count rate increase. Finally, over-fitting should be avoided (Aster et al. 2005).

The merit function \mathcal{D} is defined as

$$\mathcal{D} = \frac{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^m \left[\left(\frac{\Delta N_i}{N_i} \right)_{\text{mod}} - \left(\frac{\Delta N_i}{N_i} \right)_{\text{meas}} \right]^2}}{\sum_{i=1}^m \left(\frac{\Delta N_i}{N_i} \right)_{\text{meas}}}, \quad (4)$$

where $\left(\frac{\Delta N_i}{N_i} \right)_{\text{mod}}$ and $\left(\frac{\Delta N_i}{N_i} \right)_{\text{meas}}$ are the modelled and measured relative count rate increases of the i^{th} NM, respectively, and m is the number of the stations used in the analysis.

A reliable fit is achieved, with sustainable and smooth convergence of the optimisation, leading to a robust solution and satisfactory fit of the experimental data, when $\mathcal{D} \leq 5\text{--}10\%$ (Vashenyuk et al. 2006; Mishev & Usoskin 2016a). However \mathcal{D} could be $\approx 15\text{--}20\%$ for weak GLEs (e.g. Dennis & Schnabel 1996; Mishev et al. 2018), still providing reasonable results. Herein, the optimisation procedure uses the Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm (Levenberg 1944; Marquardt 1963) and includes also the Ridge regression (Tikhonov et al. 1995; Johansen 1997; Leonov & Yagola 1998; Huber 2019). This allowed us to unfold the SEP spectra in the case of marginal count rate increases of the NMs considered in the analysis presented here (Engl et al. 1996; Yagola et al. 2002; Mishev et al. 2005), with good accuracy (Yagola et al. 2002).

As a result, this expanded approach in GLE modelling, with explicit incorporation of magnetospheric dynamics, improves the accuracy of SEP spectral and angular reconstruction.

3 Results

In this section, we present the methodology for analysing high-energy SEP events using the global NM network together with spacecraft measurements. The approach is first illustrated through the complex and well-studied case of GLE71 on 17 May 2012 (see details in Mishev et al. 2021), which serves as a benchmark for demonstrating the diagnostic capabilities of the method under conditions of strong anisotropy and multifaceted particle transport. We then apply the same methodology to two additional events investigated within SPEARHEAD: the notable GLE74 on 11 May 2024 and the sub-GLE of 7 March 2012. These three events were selected to demonstrate the applicability of the method across a wide dynamic range of SEP intensities—from strong, highly anisotropic GLEs to weak, short-duration sub-GLEs—and to highlight the effectiveness of combining NM observations with spacecraft measurements. GLE71 exhibits pronounced anisotropy, with significant fluxes arriving from both sunward and anti-sunward directions, reflecting complex interplanetary transport conditions. GLE74, on top of similar bi-directional fluxes, occurred during highly disturbed interplanetary and geomagnetic conditions, which makes the analysis of this event particularly challenging, i.e., to derive properly the contribution of SEP to the NM count rate increase on one hand, and model the geomagnetospheric conditions on the other hand. The sub-GLE represents a weak event with subtle NM signals, pushing the limits of detection and highlighting the importance of advanced analysis techniques and cross-validation with satellite data. Together, these events demonstrate the diagnostic power of the NM network when combined with spacecraft observations such as those of PAMELA and GOES, and emphasise the need to account for particle anisotropy during the early phases of SEP events. In addition, it should be emphasised that the YF, used in the NM modelling across all three events, is newly calibrated with particle measurements with PAMELA and AMS-02.

3.1 GLE71 on May 17, 2012

This event was associated with a moderately strong M5.1-class solar flare and a fast Coronal Mass Ejection (CME) originating from NOAA Active Region 11476, located at heliographic coordinates N07W88. The flare peaked at 01:25 UT, and the CME's eruption site was magnetically well connected to Earth due to its western location, facilitating the prompt arrival of SEPs along IMF lines (Gopalswamy et al. 2013). Approximately 25 minutes later, around 01:50 UT, the global NM network registered the first clear GLE signal since December 2006. The increase in count rates persisted for about one hour, marking a relatively short but intense event. The highest responses were observed at South Pole (SOPO), Oulu, and Apatity neutron monitors, with peak relative increases of up to 22% (Papaioannou et al. 2014). Conversely, other stations recorded only modest enhancements of a few percent, indicating a highly anisotropic particle arrival, especially during the initial phase (Plainaki et al. 2014; Mishev et al. 2014). *This anisotropy is among the most complex observed in recent GLEs.*

The derived asymptotic directions for selected NMs during the peak phase (02:00 UT) are illustrated in Fig. 3. The asymptotic directions are shown for a rigidity range of 1–3 GV, with SOPO extending down to ~ 0.7 GV. Overlaid are pitch angle contours centered on the deduced axis of symmetry, derived from ACE spacecraft IMF data (taken by Mishev et al. (2021)).

Figure 3: Asymptotic directions for selected NM stations during GLE # 71 on May 17, 2012 at 02:00 UT. The standard abbreviations, the corresponding color lines and numbers indicate the NM stations and asymptotic directions, which are plotted in the rigidity range $\sim 1 - 3$ GV, while SOPO is plotted in the rigidity range $\sim 0.7 - 3$ GV. The cross corresponds to the IMF direction on the basis of ACE satellite measurements. The lines of equal pitch angles relative to the derived anisotropy axis are plotted for 15° , 30° , 45° , 60° and 90° for sunward directions (solid lines), and 165° , 150° and 120° , for the anti-Sun direction (dashed lines). See details in Mishev et al. (2021)

To characterize the SEP spectrum, for this particular event, we employed a modified power-law rigidity

spectrum form which proved to be the optimal/best fit. Its formula is given below:

$$J_{||}(P) = J_0 P^{-(\gamma + \delta\gamma(P-1))} \quad (5)$$

where $J_{||}(P)$ is the particle flux with given rigidity P in [GV] arriving from the Sun along the axis of symmetry, which is defined by the geographic coordinate angles Ψ and Λ (latitude and longitude). In Eq. 5, γ is the power-law spectral exponent at rigidity $P = 1$ GV, accordingly $\delta\gamma$ is the rate of the spectrum steepening. The angular distribution of the arriving SEPs is depicted by complicated PAD, namely superposition of two Gaussians:

$$G(\alpha(P)) \sim \exp(-\alpha^2/\sigma_1^2) + B \cdot \exp(-(\alpha - \alpha')^2/\sigma_2^2) \quad (6)$$

here α is the pitch angle, σ_1 and σ_2 are parameters corresponding to the width of the pitch angle distribution, B and α' are parameters corresponding to the contribution of the second Gaussian, including direction nearly opposite to the derived axis of symmetry. This bi-directional PAD is consistent with SEP backscattering or complex transport effects in the interplanetary medium (see relevant discussion and references in Mishev & Usoskin 2020; Rouillard et al. 2016; Papaioannou et al. 2025).

Fig. 4 shows the temporal evolution of the SEP spectra and PADs for successive 5-minute intervals, capturing the dynamic development of anisotropy and spectral softening of GLE71.

SEP fluences are derived from NM analysis combined with measurements from the PAMELA satellite. PAMELA's in situ observations provide high-precision measurements up to ~ 2 GV, offering a valuable benchmark for NM-derived spectra (Bruno et al. 2018). A good agreement in the overlapping energy range is achieved as shown in Fig. 5.

3.2 The special case of GLE 74 on May 11, 2024

A notable GLE, caused by SEPs, occurred on May 11, 2024, during the SPEARHEAD project. It was observed during a deep phase of a particularly strong Forbush decrease and one of the strongest observed geomagnetic storms. In May 2024, the Sun produced several M and X-class flares, accompanied by CMEs. These active processes disturbed the interplanetary and geomagnetospheric conditions. Particularly, a G5-class geomagnetic storm that lasted from May 10–13, 2024, peaked on May 11, 2024, with a Disturbance Storm Time (Dst) index of -412 nT. A deep Forbush decrease was also present prior to the event.

On the ground, the GLE onset was observed by the bulk of NM stations. The event revealed a gradual increase and notable anisotropy (Papaioannou et al. 2025). A careful study of the available NM records implies the presence of SEPs with rigidity up to at least ~ 2 GV. We emphasize that the determination of arrival times and amplitudes of count rate increases at different NMs was rather difficult, because SEPs propagated under disturbed conditions due to the sequence of preceding CMEs, the mentioned above FD, and the severe geomagnetic storm (Hayakawa et al. 2025). The latter led to a reduction in cutoff rigidity, specifically on mid-latitude NMs, contributing to the increase of stations' count rates on top of the SEP signal. The strongest count rate increases were detected by high-altitude Antarctic stations, namely Dome C (DOMC) $\approx 10.0\%$ and South Pole (SOPO) $\approx 7.7\%$. We note that lead-free (bare) NMs recorded greater count rate increases, namely DOMB) $\approx 16.0\%$ and South Pole Bare (SOPB) $\approx 8.9\%$.

To reveal the characteristics of SEPs that led to this GLE, as a first step, we deduced the actual signal due to SEP incidence. For this purpose, we parameterised the recovery of the FD similarly and also accounted for the increase in the NM count rate due to the reduction in cut-off rigidity by employing the magnetospheric modelling results. Hence, we can proceed further with de-trended NM count rates, that is, the count rate increase is attributed to the SEP contribution.

Using de-trended records from NMs (Usoskin et al. 2020), by employing the method described in Section 2, we derived the spectra and angular distribution of SEPs during the event under study. The best fit of the SEP spectra with $P > 1$ GV was described by a modified power-law:

Figure 4: Derived SEP rigidity spectra (left panel) and PADs (right panel) during GLE # 71 on May 17, 2012. The black solid line denotes the GCR flux, which corresponds to the time period of the event occurrence. Time (UT) refers to the end of the corresponding five-minute interval over which the data are integrated. See details in [Mishev et al. \(2021\)](#)

$$j_{\parallel}(P) = j_0 P^{-(\gamma + \delta\gamma(P-1))} \quad (7)$$

where j_{\parallel} is the flux of particles with rigidity P in GV along the axis of symmetry identified by geographic latitude Ψ and longitude Λ and the power-law exponent is γ with the steepening $\delta\gamma$. At $P \leq 1$ GV, the rigidity spectrum of SEPs is approximated with:

$$j_{\parallel}(P) = j_0 P^{-(\gamma + \delta\gamma P)} \quad (8)$$

The PAD was approximated with a double Gaussian:

$$G(\alpha) \propto \exp(-\alpha^2/\sigma_1^2) + B \cdot \exp(-(\alpha - \pi)^2/\sigma_2^2), \quad (9)$$

where α is the pitch angle between the axis of symmetry of the particle distribution and the asymptotic viewing direction at rigidity P , associated with the arrival direction ([Cramp et al. 1997](#)), and σ_1 is a parameter determining the PAD width. The terms B and σ_2 account for the normalisation and PAD width for particles arriving from the anti-Sun direction.

An illustration of the derived spectra and PAD throughout the event is given in Fig. 6. The derived SEP spectra revealed moderate hardness, that is, with spectral indices γ ranging from about 5 to about

Figure 5: Angle-, energy-, and time-integrated SEP fluence during GLE71 derived with NM analysis (blue line), compared with PAMELA measurements (blue hatched area), as depicted in the legend. The filled and hatched area correspond to the PAMELA data up to 2 GV and data extrapolation above 2 GV respectively. Adapted by Koldobskiy & Mishev (2022).

6.3, during the event onset and late phase, respectively. The spectra gradually softened throughout the event. A notable steepening of the SEP spectra $\delta\gamma$, that is, a roll-off, was revealed, specifically during the initial (hard SEP spectra, gradually rising flux) and the main phase of the event (moderately hard spectra, maximal flux). This roll-off of the SEP spectra persisted throughout the whole event, even in the late phase (soft spectra, gradually diminishing flux).

We compared our reconstructions with in situ measurements by GOES satellite, using data from the SGPS detector (Kress et al. 2021) of GOES-16, and employing the method of SEP identification and integral flux calculation similar to Raukunen et al. (2022). We computed the time-integrated fluence of particles throughout the event following the methodology of (Koldobskiy et al. 2021). Figure 7 presents the results of these computations. Overall, there is a good agreement between GOES SGPS measurements and NM reconstructions.

3.3 The sub-GLE on March 7, 2012

The event of March 7, 2012 is recognized as a notable sub-GLE, which refers to SEP events where the particle fluxes are insufficient to produce a significant global response at ground-based NMs but can still be detected by a few high-sensitivity stations. Sub-GLEs provide crucial insight into SEP acceleration and propagation processes, particularly near the threshold of ground detectability.

This event originated from NOAA Active Region 11429, which was located at N17E15 on the visible solar disk. The region produced an extremely intense X5.4-class solar flare, peaking at 00:24 UT, fol-

Figure 6: Selected reconstructed rigidity spectra (left panel) and PADs (right panel) of SEPs during GLE #74. Adapted from [Papaioannou et al. \(2025\)](#)

lowed by a full-halo CME with a plane-of-sky speed exceeding 2500 km/s, as observed by the LASCO coronagraph on board SOHO ([Gopalswamy et al. 2014](#)) followed by a consequent X1.3-class flare with a similarly fast CME ([Patsourakos et al. 2016](#)). These strong flares and fast CMEs were associated with efficient particle acceleration in the solar corona and interplanetary space. The energetic particle injection led to a substantial enhancement in proton fluxes observed by GOES-13 and GOES-15 at energies exceeding 100 MeV, beginning shortly after the first flare and CME onset. The $E > 10$ MeV proton flux reached peak values of approximately 3000 particle flux units (pfus), indicating a major SEP event in space. However, the flux of relativistic protons (rigidity $R > 1$ GV), necessary for ground detection, remained relatively low. A comprehensive Sun-to-Earth investigation of this event was provided by [Patsourakos et al. \(2016\)](#). Their multi-spacecraft analysis showed that only the second CME (associated with the X1.3 flare) was Earth-directed, causing the main geomagnetic impacts ~ 2 days later, including a Dst depression to -148 nT driven by the storm-time interplanetary CME (ICME) triggered on March 7. This sub-GLE exemplifies a complex, borderline ground-level event—characterized by intense CMEs, robust flare activity, but only modest relativistic SEP penetration.

A similar analysis, as for GLE71 and GLE74 detailed here above, was performed for the sub-GLE event on March 7, 2012. Fig. 8 illustrates the comparison of NM-derived proton flux with data from GOES spacecraft, showing consistent spectral shapes in overlapping rigidity intervals.

3.4 Comparing with SOHO/EPHIN

Since SPEARHEAD delivered novel datasets that substantially extend the accessible energy range of standard spaceborne particle instrumentation toward higher energies, a comprehensive second-level inter-comparison was performed. These extended measurements enable a detailed cross-instrument

Figure 7: Omnidirectional SEP fluence as reconstructed by SGPS GOES and NM full analysis in 1-hour intervals. Three time-stamps on 11 May 2024 are presented. One at 02:00 UT (light green), one at 03:00 UT (dark green) and one at 04:00 UT (gray). For GOES SGPS each point (circle) corresponds to a mean channel energy ranging from a few ten’s to a few hundred MeV. NM reconstructions start at E=400 MeV and the overlap is clearly identifiable.

validation that would not be possible using conventional datasets alone. In particular, proton observations from SOHO/EPHIN, provided within the framework of Work Package (WP)2, offer a unique opportunity for direct comparison with contemporaneous measurements from GOES, including EPEAD, HEPAD, and SEISS. The overlapping energy coverage between these instruments allows for a systematic assessment of measurement consistency, spectral continuity, and potential systematic differences across platforms. Such cross-calibration is essential for constructing reliable broadband energy spectra and for constraining the behaviour of high-energy SEP populations, where instrumental limitations often introduce uncertainties in spectral slope and rollover determination.

In the following, detailed comparisons are presented for both GLE74 (11 May 2024) and the sub-GLE event of 7 March 2012. The analysis combines (i) time–intensity profiles in overlapping energy channels and (ii) the temporal evolution of the differential energy spectra, thereby linking intensity variations directly to spectral changes.

3.4.1 GLE74 on May 11, 2024

Figure 9 shows the time profiles (left panel) and corresponding hourly energy spectra (right panel) for GLE74, derived from SOHO/EPHIN and GOES/SEISS.

Figure 8: Comparison between GOES (squares) and NM (dashed lines) data analysis for the sub-GLE event on 7 March 2012. Here spacecraft data cover the energy range from ten to 200 MeV (squares), while reconstructions from the NM network start at 400 MeV. Different colors correspond to different time-stamps as explained in the legend.

Temporal evolution. The time–intensity profiles reveal a coherent large-scale evolution across all energies. A rapid rise begins shortly after 02:00–03:00 UT, followed by a broad maximum and a gradual decay phase. Despite this overall agreement, clear differences appear in the detailed morphology of the rising phase. Several GOES channels, particularly P7–P9, exhibit a pronounced “bump-like” enhancement during the early rise, whereas the corresponding EPHIN channels show a smoother and more monotonic increase. Although the peak fluxes occur within a similar time window, the fine temporal structure differs between the instruments. This structured enhancement observed by GOES may reflect energy-dependent injection, evolving pitch-angle anisotropies, multi-step acceleration processes, or differences in instrumental response and effective energy definitions (see also Papaioannou et al. 2025).

Spectral evolution. The spectral evolution provides complementary insight into these temporal features. At all times, the spectra display a monotonic decrease with increasing energy, consistent with power-law-like behavior typical of SEP events. During the early phase (02:00–05:00 UT), the flux increases across the entire energy range, in agreement with the rapid intensity rise seen in the time profiles (see also Section 5). However, the enhancement is energy dependent: the high-energy portion of the spectrum strengthens more strongly relative to lower energies, resulting in gradual spectral hardening. This indicates either increasing acceleration efficiency to several hundred MeV or improving magnetic connectivity to the acceleration region.

As the event progresses (approximately 06:00–09:00 UT; see Section 5), the spectral shape becomes comparatively stable while the flux remains elevated, corresponding to the broad plateau seen in the time profiles. During the late phase, flux levels decrease at all energies and the spectra soften slightly, consistent with transport-dominated evolution once injection weakens.

Figure 9: Temporal evolution comparison between **GOES** (blue line) and **EPHIN** (orange line) for a set of three differential energies (panel on the left). Spectral evolution of **GLE74** from **GOES** (black filled circles) and **EPHIN** (green filled circles) at two hourly intervals: 03:00-04:00 UT and 07:00-08:00 UT, respectively (panel on the right).

In the overlapping energy range between roughly 80 and 200 MeV, the spectra derived from **EPHIN** and **GOES/SEISS** show very good agreement in spectral slope. Small differences in absolute flux level, typically within a factor of two, remain but do not affect the overall spectral continuity. This consistency demonstrates that both instruments observe the same high-energy proton population and validates the combination of datasets to extend the spectral coverage toward higher energies.

Combined temporal and spectral interpretation. Taken together, the time-profile and spectral analyses show that the event evolution cannot be described as a simple uniform increase in flux. Instead, the rising phase is characterized by both a strong intensity enhancement and a concurrent spectral hardening, while the main phase exhibits a comparatively steady spectral form. The structured bump seen in the **GOES** time profiles coincides with the period of most rapid spectral evolution, suggesting that short-timescale variations in injection or anisotropy may imprint themselves most clearly at intermediate energies. Overall, the strong agreement in global trends between **GOES/SEISS** and **SOHO/EPHIN** supports the robustness of the reconstructed spectra, while the differences in fine temporal structure highlight the importance of considering both instrumental and physical effects when interpreting the early phase of the event.

3.4.2 sub-GLE on March 7, 2012

Figure 10 presents the time-intensity profiles (left panel) and the corresponding sequence of hourly differential energy spectra (right panel) for the sub-GLE event on 7 March 2012, derived from **SOHO/EPHIN** and **GOES** (**EPEAD** and **HEPAD**).

Temporal evolution. The time-intensity profiles show a gradual rise beginning shortly after 05:00–06:00 UT, with fluxes increasing coherently across all examined energy channels (see details in Sec-

Figure 10: Temporal evolution comparison between **GOES** (blue line) and **EPHIN** (orange line) for a set of three differential energies (panel on the left). Spectral evolution of sub-GLE from **GOES**, **EPEAD** (black filled circles) and **HEPAD** (red filled circles), and **SOHO/EPHIN** (green filled circles) at two hourly intervals: 06:00-07:00 UT and 10:00-11:00 UT, respectively (panel on the right)

tion 5). In contrast to **GLE74**, the rise phase is smoother and does not exhibit pronounced “bump-like” substructure. The intensity increase appears ordered in energy, with lower-energy channels reaching enhanced levels earlier and attaining higher absolute fluxes, while the highest-energy channels respond more moderately.

The event reaches its maximum flux levels between approximately 10:00 and 12:00 UT, depending on energy. At intermediate energies (e.g., ~ 60 – 170 MeV), **GOES** and **EPHIN** show very similar temporal behavior, including comparable rise rates and peak timing. At higher energies ($\gtrsim 300$ MeV), the flux enhancement remains modest and decays more rapidly, consistent with the classification of this event as a sub-GLE rather than a full GLE.

Overall, the temporal evolution is characterized by a smooth rise, a relatively broad maximum, and a gradual decay phase extending into the late hours of the day. No strong secondary peaks or abrupt transitions are evident in the high-energy channels.

Spectral evolution. The sequence of hourly energy spectra from 05:00–06:00 UT through 18:00–19:00 UT illustrates the evolution of the broadband proton distribution from the early rise phase to the decay phase.

During the earliest intervals (05:00–07:00 UT), the spectra are relatively soft, with steep slopes and comparatively weak high-energy fluxes. As the event develops (08:00–12:00 UT), fluxes increase across the entire energy range, but the enhancement is not uniform: the mid-energy range (~ 80 – 200 MeV) strengthens more prominently than the highest-energy channels measured by **HEPAD**. This leads to moderate spectral hardening during the rise phase, although the high-energy tail remains significantly suppressed compared to typical large GLE events.

Around the time of maximum intensity (approximately 10:00–12:00 UT), the spectra approach a quasi-

stationary shape. The spectral slopes derived from [SOHO/EPHIN](#) and [GOES/EPEAD](#) are generally consistent in the overlapping energy range, demonstrating good cross-instrument agreement. Differences in absolute normalization remain within expected systematic uncertainties and do not affect the overall spectral form.

At energies above ~ 300 MeV, the [GOES/HEPAD](#) points lie well below an extrapolation of the mid-energy power-law trend, indicating a clear spectral steepening or rollover at high energies. This high-energy suppression persists throughout the event and becomes more pronounced during the decay phase (after $\sim 13:00$ UT; not shown), when fluxes decrease at all energies and the spectra soften gradually.

Combined temporal and spectral interpretation. Taken together, the time profiles and spectral sequence indicate that the sub-[GLE](#) event is characterized by a relatively smooth and gradual acceleration and transport scenario. The rise phase is accompanied by moderate spectral hardening, reflecting an increasing contribution of higher-energy particles, but the acceleration efficiency above several hundred MeV remains limited. The absence of strong high-energy fluxes and the persistent spectral steepening above ~ 300 MeV explain why this event did not produce a pronounced ground-level signal.

The good agreement between [SOHO/EPHIN](#) and [GOES](#) in the overlapping energy ranges supports the reliability of the reconstructed spectra and confirms that both instruments observe a consistent proton population. At the same time, the systematic high-energy rollover seen in the [HEPAD](#) channels provides clear evidence that the particle distribution during this event is intrinsically softer than that of major [GLEs](#).

In summary, the 7 March 2012 sub-[GLE](#) exhibits coherent temporal evolution across instruments, moderate spectral hardening during the rise phase, and a pronounced high-energy steepening that limits the production of relativistic particles. This behavior clearly distinguishes it from the more energetic and spectrally harder [GLE74](#) event.

4 Conclusions

In this report, we present and apply a unified methodology for analysing high-energy SEP events using the global NM network in combination with space-borne measurements. The approach is first demonstrated through a detailed showcase study of GLE71, which provides an ideal benchmark for illustrating the diagnostic capabilities and limitations of the method. GLE71 exhibited a highly complex and evolving angular distribution, including significant sunward and anti-sunward flux components with a measurable directional shift during the event. From this case study, we demonstrate how the methodology can reliably reconstruct spectral and angular characteristics, validate them through comparison with PAMELA observations, and capture the effects of interplanetary transport processes such as scattering, magnetic field turbulence, and topology changes.

Building on the insights gained from GLE71, we apply the same methodology to two additional events: GLE74 and the sub-GLE of 7 March 2012. GLE74 occurred under highly disturbed interplanetary and geomagnetic conditions, presenting a challenging environment for both NM detection and geomagnetic modelling. Nevertheless, the methodology proved robust, enabling us to separate the SEP-induced count-rate increases from the concurrent strong Forbush decrease and to characterize the anisotropic particle flux. In addition, a detailed inter-comparison between SOHO/EPHIN and GOES measurements was performed for this event. The overlapping energy coverage allowed for a systematic validation of spectral continuity and intensity levels across independent spacecraft. Despite differences in fine temporal structure and small normalization offsets, the two instruments showed consistent spectral slopes and coherent temporal evolution, strengthening confidence in the reconstructed high-energy proton spectra and supporting their use in broadband spectral modelling.

The sub-GLE, in contrast, represents a weak event with subtle NM signatures near the limits of detectability. Its analysis underscores the importance of advanced inversion techniques and careful cross-validation with space-borne measurements. In this case, the combined use of GOES and SOHO/EPHIN data proved essential for identifying and characterizing the weak high-energy proton component. The spectral comparison revealed a clear high-energy steepening above a few hundred MeV, consistent with the limited relativistic particle production inferred from the NM response. The good agreement between EPHIN and GOES in the overlapping energy range further confirms the reliability of the derived spectra, even in marginal events.

Together, these case studies demonstrate the diagnostic power and flexibility of the global NM network when integrated with spacecraft observations such as PAMELA, GOES, and SOHO/EPHIN. They highlight the critical importance of accounting for particle anisotropy—particularly during the early phases of SEP events—and show how cross-instrument spectral validation enhances the robustness of high-energy reconstructions. The established methodology can therefore be applied across a wide range of event intensities and heliospheric conditions, from strong and highly anisotropic GLEs to weak sub-GLEs near detection threshold.

This report represents **Deliverable 3.4 (D3.4)** of the SPEARHEAD project, aimed at advancing the reconstruction and physical interpretation of high-energy SEPs through the combined use of ground-based and space-borne diagnostics.

5 Appendix

Here we present the expanded time-evolution of the spectrum for both GLE74 (Figure 11) and the sub-GLE on 07 March 2012 (Figure 12), tracing the development of the particle distribution from onset to decay. The time-resolved spectra reveal clear changes in intensity and slope throughout each event. GLE74 shows a pronounced early hardening followed by gradual softening, consistent with strong acceleration and subsequent transport effects. In contrast, the sub-GLE exhibits lower overall fluxes and a steeper high-energy decline, reflecting its limited relativistic proton production. The comparison between GOES and SOHO/EPHIN in overlapping energy ranges provides an important cross-validation of these results. Despite small differences in absolute intensity and fine temporal structure, both instruments show consistent spectral evolution and slope behavior.

Figure 11: Comparison between spectra derived from GOES/SEISS (black filled circles) and EPHIN (green filled circles) for the GLE74. Each panel corresponds to 1 hour, denoted on its top.

Figure 12: Comparison between spectra derived from GOES/EPEAD (black filled circles) HEPAD (red filled circles) and EPHIN (green filled circles) for the sub-GLE event on 7 March 2012. Each panel corresponds to 1 hour, denoted on its top.

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